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Enhancing Robustness in Feature Importance Methods with NAFIC and CESHAP for Improved Interpretability

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ABSTRACT

Understanding and interpreting machine learning models is crucial in high-stakes industries like steel manufacturing, where decisions impact energy efficiency and environmental sustainability. Traditional feature importance methods often struggle with robustness under noisy conditions, leading to unreliable insights. To address this problem, we introduce the Complexity and Interaction Enhanced SHAP (CESHAP), a novel feature importance method that incorporates model complexity and feature interactions. Alongside, we propose the Noise-Adjusted Feature Importance Change (NAFIC) metric to assess the robustness of feature importance methods against varying levels of noise. Experiments conducted on an energy consumption dataset from the steel industry, with systematically introduced Gaussian noise levels (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%), demonstrate that CESHAP offers superior robustness in tree-based models compared to SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) and Permutation Feature Importance (PFI). Our findings underscore the effectiveness of CESHAP in enhancing interpretability and reliability in complex, non-linear models, ultimately supporting more informed decision-making in energy-intensive industries.

Introduction

The steel industry is one of the most energy-intensive sectors, accounting for approximately 7–9% of global carbon dioxide emissions due to its reliance on fossil fuels and the energy demands of its production processes (World Steel Association 2016). The production of steel involves several stages, including the extraction of raw materials, their processing in blast furnaces, and the final refining and rolling of steel products. Each of these stages is energy-intensive, and any inefficiencies can lead to significant increases in energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions (Danny Harvey 2024).

Efforts to improve energy efficiency in the steel industry have been crucial in addressing its environmental impact. Traditional approaches often focus on

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optimizing operational processes, such as recycling waste heat or implementing energy-efficient technologies in blast furnaces. However, these methods have limitations due to the increasing complexity of production processes and the vast amounts of data generated in modern steel manufacturing. The need for advanced solutions that can handle complex data and provide actionable insights has become more pressing. In this context, machine learning models have emerged as powerful tools for predicting energy consumption, detecting anomalies, and identifying factors contributing to inefficiencies. Yet, the “black-box” nature of many machine learning models poses challenges for interpretability, which is essential for trust and decision-making in industrial settings (Arrieta et al. 2020).

Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) methods have been developed to address the interpretability challenges of machine learning models (Arrieta et al. 2020; Coroama and Groza 2022). However, *robustness metrics* for XAI, those assessing whether explanations remain stable under data noise or perturbations, remain underexplored in real-world industrial contexts such as steel manufacturing. Current evaluation criteria may not fully capture the high variability, multi-step production processes, and inherently noisy sensor data prevalent in steel mills (Arrieta et al. 2020). Consequently, even small errors in feature importance explanations can undermine crucial decisions on energy optimization, potentially leading to cost overruns and increased greenhouse gas emissions.

Recent studies have proposed various metrics for evaluating XAI methods, categorized into aspects such as correctness, robustness, and interpretability (Arrieta et al. 2020; Coroama and Groza 2022). For instance, Arrieta et al. (2020) present a taxonomy of XAI evaluation metrics, including fidelity (how accurately the explanations reflect the model’s decision process), consistency (the stability of explanations across similar inputs), and comprehensibility (the ease with which humans can understand the explanations). Additionally, robustness metrics assess the sensitivity of explanations to input perturbations, highlighting the need for explanations that remain consistent even when the data is subject to noise or minor changes (Coroama and Groza 2022). Despite these developments, there remains a gap in metrics that adequately account for the inherent noise and complexity in industrial datasets, and that are applicable across different models and explanation methods. In steel production, which can involve fluctuating furnace operations and rapidly changing feedstock quality, unreliable XAI outputs can directly cause misguided interventions, raising operational expenses and environmental footprints.

In the era of big data and complex machine learning models, the robustness of feature importance methods is paramount to ensure that interpretations are reliable and actionable (Doshi-Velez and Kim 2017). As highlighted by Arrieta et al. (2020), robustness refers to the stability of explanations in the presence of data perturbations or adversarial attacks. In industrial applications like the

steel industry, data is often noisy, multi-faceted, and may contain strong feature interactions due to complex production pipelines (Hooker, Mentch, and Zhou 2021). Consequently, traditional feature importance techniques can provide inconsistent explanations under these conditions, limiting their effectiveness for process optimization. Robust interpretability not only helps operators pinpoint critical factors affecting energy usage but also mitigates the risk of overlooking latent inefficiencies that could lead to extended production times and higher emissions.

In this study, we address these challenges by introducing the NAFIC metric, a model-agnostic evaluation metric designed to assess the robustness of feature importance methods under noisy conditions. NAFIC quantifies the sensitivity of feature importance values to noise, helping to determine whether interpretability methods maintain consistent explanations across different data perturbations. Additionally, we introduce CESHAP, an enhanced version of the SHAP method that integrates model complexity and feature interactions into its calculation of feature importance. By addressing the limitations of traditional SHAP, CESHAP offers more stable and robust feature importance scores, especially in noisy environments. Together, NAFIC and CESHAP provide a comprehensive framework for robust and reliable feature importance analysis in complex, real-world scenarios.

To address the challenges outlined, our study seeks to advance the field of feature importance evaluation by tackling the limitations inherent in existing methods. Traditional feature importance approaches often fail to maintain robustness and reliability in the presence of noisy data, a critical drawback in complex industrial applications such as steel manufacturing. Inspired by prior work, such as the framework proposed by Lu et al. (2021), which leverages joint norms minimization for robust feature selection, our research builds upon this foundation by focusing on interpretability and robustness in noisy environments. Unlike feature selection methods that emphasize minimizing reconstruction error and regularization, we aim to improve the stability and reliability of feature importance scores under data perturbations. By introducing the NAFIC metric and CESHAP, we address these gaps by providing robust and interpretable evaluations of feature importance methods across varying noise levels and data complexities, ensuring they are well-suited for real-world industrial challenges. This approach contributes to the development of explainable, reliable, and actionable insights for complex machine learning applications.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: “Introduction” introduces the topic and objectives of the research. “Related work” provides an overview of the recent state-of-the-art literature. “Methodology” details the methodologies employed, including evaluation metrics and feature importance methods, as well as introduces the NAFIC metric and the CESHAP

method. “Experimental setup” outlines the experimental setup. “Limitations” discusses the limitations of this study. Finally, “Conclusions” summarizes conclusions and suggests future research directions.

Related work

Model-agnostic feature importance methods

Several methods have been developed to assess feature importance, each with its strengths and limitations. PFI is a model-agnostic approach that measures the change in model performance when the values of a feature are randomly permuted. This method provides an intuitive understanding of feature importance but can be computationally expensive and sensitive to data permutation (Altmann et al. 2010). PFI was chosen for this study due to its simplicity and broad applicability across different model types, making it a widely-used benchmark for evaluating feature importance. Its model-agnostic nature allows us to apply it consistently across various models, providing a comparative baseline to assess the robustness of more complex methods. Additionally, PFI provides a global perspective on feature importance, offering insights into the overall impact of each feature on the model’s performance (Breiman 2001).

SHAP is another popular method that leverages cooperative game theory to attribute the contribution of each feature to the prediction. SHAP values offer consistency and local accuracy, ensuring that the sum of feature contributions equals the model’s output (Lundberg and Lee 2017). However, calculating SHAP values can be computationally intensive, especially for complex models. SHAP was selected for this study because of its theoretical foundation in game theory, which provides a comprehensive and consistent approach to feature importance. The method’s ability to explain individual predictions with high precision makes it particularly valuable for understanding complex models, where feature interactions and non-linear effects are prominent. By including SHAP in our evaluation, we aim to explore its robustness under noisy conditions and compare its performance against simpler methods like PFI. Furthermore, SHAP provides both local and global perspectives on feature importance, making it a versatile tool for comprehensive model interpretation (Lundberg et al. 2019).

Other explanation techniques

There are several methodologies that were employed for explaining decisions on machine learning models. Some of the first ones were LRP – Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (Bach et al. 2015), LIME – Local Interpretable Model-

Agnostic Explanations (Ribeiro, Singh, and Guestrin 2016a), GraphLIME (Huang et al. 2020).

LIME (Ribeiro, Singh, and Guestrin 2016a) is a model-agnostic explanation method providing flexible and widely applicable explanations, while treating machine learning models as black boxes using interpretable models to approximate their behavior.

GraphLIME (Huang et al. 2020) is an explanation method for graph neural networks (GNNs) that extends LIME by using a non-linear approach. It samples features from its neighbors in order to predict a node. Additionally, it trains an interpretable Lasso model to identify the features that affect more the prediction based on the complex interactions within the graph.

Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) (Bach et al. 2015) is an explanation method that uses a model's internal structure in order to provide insights into predictions by redistributing relevance values backward through the layers to show how much each input contributed. The model's structure and the iterative process conserves relevance enabling explanations that highlight features supporting or opposing the prediction.

Interpretability in deep learning and the role of attention mechanisms

While our study focuses on tree-based and linear models, deep learning approaches have also seen increasing use for tasks requiring both high predictive power and interpretability. One prominent strategy is the attention mechanism, which allocates different “weights” or “attention” to input components, thereby highlighting the most influential parts of the data (Hu and Xie 2025; Mohanty et al. 2024). Attention-enabled models can inherently provide a form of interpretability, as the attention weights often signal which inputs drive the model's output most strongly.

Graph Attention Networks (GATs) extend the attention mechanism to graph-structured data (Hu and Xie 2025). By enabling each node to focus on the most relevant neighbors, GATs produce attention scores that can be interpreted as edge-level importance. In the context of traffic or other industrial network scenarios, such as supply chain logistics, these attention coefficients help identify crucial relational patterns, potentially complementing or inspiring methods like CESHAP or NAFIC.

Another line of research uses soft attention for image or sequence data (Mohanty et al. 2024). Here, features in an image (e.g., MRI scans) or tokens in a sequence (e.g., language data) are weighted based on their relevance. This weighting not only improves predictive performance but also adds interpretability by exposing which pixels or segments are attended to most intensely. Similar to how we measure robustness under noise, interpretability in attention-based models may also involve noise insertion in attention maps or hidden representations, helping to assess stability.

Although attention maps are sometimes described as an “explanation” of the model’s prediction, there is debate over whether these maps truly reflect causal importance or simply correlate with it (Guesmi, Suresh Aswani, and Shafique 2024; Li et al. 2021). Recent findings have illustrated that attention alone may be insufficient or even misleading as a faithful explanation of the model’s decision boundaries (Jaakkola and Alvarez Melis 2018; Slack, Singh, and Sharma 2020). Some argue that attention is not inherently explainable. Nonetheless, attention-based visualization does offer a direct, model-internal indicator of feature weighting. For extremely deep or complex architectures, additional post-hoc methods – like our proposed NAFIC or more advanced saliency-based approaches – could be layered onto attention outputs to assess how stable these visual “explanations” are in the presence of noisy inputs.

In industrial manufacturing, applying attention-based deep learning remains a promising avenue for complex, multivariate sensor data. Although we have not specifically implemented an attention-based model here, the design principles of CESHAP – especially its emphasis on feature interactions – may resonate with attention’s goals. As we expand our framework to deep neural networks in future work, attention scores could be integrated with or compared to CESHAP-style metrics, giving an even deeper view of model behavior. Indeed, combining attention with measures like NAFIC might help detect noise sensitivity in early layers of a model, opening the door to more robust interpretability in high-stakes industries.

Challenges in robustness of interpretability methods

Although feature importance methods, such as PFI and SHAP, offer valuable insights into model interpretability, they face significant challenges in terms of robustness, particularly in noisy environments. Models can be highly sensitive to small perturbations in the data, leading to fluctuating importance scores and undermining the reliability of these methods (Fisher, Rudin, and Dominici 2019). To address this, there is a need for methods that account for additional model characteristics, such as complexity and interaction effects, to enhance stability and consistency (Guidotti et al. 2018).

Methodology

Detailed description of PFI and SHAP

PFI is a model-agnostic method that evaluates the importance of a feature by measuring the change in the model’s performance when the feature’s values are randomly permuted. This approach provides an intuitive measure of feature importance by observing the degradation in model accuracy caused

by disrupting the relationship between the feature and the target variable (Altmann et al. 2010).

$$PFI(X_i) = M(D) - M(D_{X_i}^\pi) \quad (1)$$

Where $M(D)$ is the model's performance on the original data, $M(D_{X_i}^\pi)$ is the model's performance on the data where X_i has been permuted. The difference in performance between the original and permuted data signifies the importance of feature X_i as shown in Equation 1.

SHAP is a method based on cooperative game theory that provides a unified measure of feature importance by calculating the contribution of each feature to the prediction. SHAP values explain the difference between the actual prediction and the average prediction by considering all possible combinations of features (Dubey 1975).

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|!(|N| - |S| - 1)!}{|N|!} [f(S \cup \{i\}) - f(S)] \quad (2)$$

Where ϕ_i is the SHAP value for feature i , N is the set of all features, S is a subset of features excluding feature i and the term $[f(S \cup \{i\}) - f(S)]$ represents the marginal contribution of feature i when added to the subset S as shown in Equation 2.

Definition of complexity and interaction enhanced SHAP

Introduction

CESHAP is an advanced interpretability method designed to enhance the standard SHAP by incorporating additional dimensions of model complexity and feature interaction effects. In the rapidly evolving field of machine learning, the need for robust and reliable interpretability methods has become paramount. CESHAP aims to address these needs by providing more nuanced and comprehensive insights into model behavior, particularly in noisy and complex data environments.

Understanding the inner workings of machine learning models is crucial for various reasons, including model validation, debugging, and regulatory compliance. Traditional SHAP values offer a theoretically sound framework for attributing the output of a model to its input features based on cooperative game theory. However, as models become more complex and are applied to increasingly intricate datasets, the limitations of standard SHAP values become apparent.

CESHAP extends the SHAP framework by integrating measures of model complexity and feature interactions. This extension is particularly important because it accounts for the additional layers of intricacy inherent in modern machine learning models. By considering these factors, CESHAP provides

a more accurate and holistic view of feature importance, making it an invaluable tool for practitioners who require precise and reliable explanations of their models' predictions.

How CESHAP Enhances Interpretability:

- (1) CESHAP includes a complexity term that adjusts the SHAP values based on the model's decision path or depth, particularly in tree-based models. This adjustment ensures that the explanations take into account how difficult it is for the model to make a particular decision, thus reflecting the true importance of features more accurately.
- (2) Another critical enhancement in CESHAP is the inclusion of interaction effects between features. In many real-world datasets, features do not act independently; their combined effects often influence the model's predictions significantly. CESHAP captures these interactions, providing a richer and more detailed explanation of how features work together to affect the model's output.

The primary novelty of CESHAP lies in its dual focus on complexity and interaction, which addresses key limitations of traditional SHAP methods. By integrating these two dimensions, CESHAP offers several unique advantages:

- **Enhanced Robustness:** CESHAP is designed to be more robust in the presence of noisy data. By adjusting SHAP values based on model complexity and feature interactions, it mitigates the potential distortions caused by noise, leading to more stable and reliable feature importance scores.
- **Improved Stability:** The incorporation of complexity and interaction effects helps in stabilizing the feature importance scores across different models and datasets. This stability is crucial for applications where consistent interpretability is required, such as in regulatory environments or high-stakes decision-making scenarios.
- **Greater Precision:** CESHAP provides more precise explanations by capturing the subtleties of how features influence predictions in a nuanced manner. This precision is particularly beneficial for complex models where traditional methods might oversimplify the feature contributions.

CESHAP represents a significant advancement in the field of model interpretability. By building upon the established SHAP framework and addressing its limitations through the incorporation of complexity and interaction effects, CESHAP provides a more robust, stable, and precise method for understanding machine learning models as shown in Equation 3.

$$\phi_i^{CESHAP} = \phi_i \cdot \left(\frac{1 + \alpha \cdot C_i + \beta \cdot I_i}{1 + \lambda \cdot |\alpha \cdot C_i + \beta \cdot I_i|} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where ϕ is the SHAP value for feature i , C_i is the complexity of the model's decision path for feature i (e.g., the depth of the decision path in a decision tree), I_i is the interaction effect between feature i and other features (measured by SHAP interaction values), α and β are scaling parameters that control how much the complexity and interaction effects influence the final CESHAP values and λ is the regularization term to control the adjustment magnitude, ensuring that when $C(i)$ or $I(i)$ is too large, the effect of these terms is controlled. The term $(1 + \alpha \cdot C(I) + \beta \cdot I(i))$ serves as the adjustment factor, which either amplifies or reduces the original SHAP value based on the model complexity and feature interactions. The 1 represents the baseline SHAP value, and the terms $\alpha \cdot C(i)$ and $\beta \cdot I(i)$ represent additional, proportional increases based on the complexity and interaction. The computational procedure for applying this adjustment is detailed in Algorithm 1

Algorithm 1 CESHAP Adjustment of SHAP Values.

Require: SHAP values $\mathbf{S} \in R^{n \times m}$, where n is the number of samples and m is the number of features

Require: Complexity $\mathbf{C} \in R^m$, Interaction $\mathbf{I} \in R^m$

Require: Hyperparameters α, β , Regularization term λ

Ensure: Adjusted CESHAP values \mathbf{S}^{CESHAP}

```

1: Initialize  $\mathbf{S}^{CESHAP} \leftarrow \mathbf{S}$ 
2: for  $i = 1$  to  $m$  do
3:   if  $\neg \text{isNaN}(\mathbf{C}[i])$  and  $\neg \text{isNaN}(\mathbf{I}[i])$  then
4:     adjustment  $\leftarrow 1 + \alpha \cdot \mathbf{C}[i] + \beta \cdot \mathbf{I}[i]$ 
5:     adjustment  $\leftarrow \frac{\text{adjustment}}{1 + \lambda \cdot |\text{adjustment}|}$ 
6:      $\mathbf{S}^{CESHAP}[:, i] \leftarrow \mathbf{S}[:, i] \times \text{adjustment}$ 
7:   end if
8: end for
9: return  $\mathbf{S}^{CESHAP}$ 

```

In [Figure 1](#), we illustrate a conceptual flow diagram on how CESHAP adjusts standard SHAP values by incorporating model complexity and feature interaction, scaled by α, β , and regularized by λ in the adjustment stage.

Model complexity

Model complexity refers to how difficult or intricate the model's decision-making process is for a given feature. In decision tree-based models (e.g., Random Forest or Gradient Boosting), complexity is typically related to the depth of the tree at which a feature is split. The deeper a feature is in the tree, the more complex its decision path is.

Figure 1. CESHAP conceptual flow diagram.

Consider a decision tree model that splits on feature i at different depths across the trees in the ensemble. The complexity for feature i can be defined as the average depth at which feature i appears in the decision paths of all trees.

For instance, suppose feature i appears in 3 trees in a Random Forest model at the following depths:

- Tree 1: Feature i appears at Depth = 3.
- Tree 2: Feature i appears at Depth = 5.
- Tree 3: Feature i appears at Depth = 4.

The formula for complexity in this example is:

$$C(i) = \frac{\text{Sum of depths for feature } i}{\text{Number of trees where feature } i \text{ appears}}$$

The average complexity for feature i is calculated as:

$$C(i) = \frac{3}{3 + 5 + 4} = \frac{3}{12} = 4$$

Thus, the complexity score for feature i is 4, which indicates that, on average, feature i is used in splits deeper in the tree, making it more complex. In general, higher complexity means the feature plays a more intricate role in the model's decision process.

Feature interaction

Feature interaction measures how much a feature interacts with other features in the model. In SHAP, interaction effects can be captured using SHAP interaction values, which quantify how much two features jointly contribute to the prediction, over and above their individual contributions.

SHAP interaction values are represented as a matrix, where each element (i, j) captures the interaction between feature i and feature j . For example, consider a simple model with three features i , j , and k . The SHAP interaction values might look like this:

$$\text{SHAP Interaction Matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & 0.05 & 0.02 \\ 0.05 & 0.4 & 0.06 \\ 0.02 & 0.06 & 0.2 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this matrix, 0.3 represents the interaction of feature i with itself (i.e., its individual contribution), 0.05 represents the interaction between feature i and feature j and 0.02 represents the interaction between feature i and feature k .

The total interaction effect for feature i can be defined as the sum of its interactions with all other features:

$$I(i) = \sum_{j \neq i} |\text{SHAP Interaction}(i, j)|$$

For feature i , the interaction is calculated as follows:

$$I(i) = |0.05| + |0.02| = 0.07$$

Thus, the interaction score for feature i is 0.07. This value indicates how much feature i interacts with other features in the model. Higher interaction values suggest that feature i has significant dependencies with other features, affecting the model's output when combined with them.

Meaning of the regularization term λ in the equation

- $\lambda = 0$: If $\lambda = 0$, the regularization term disappears, and the equation relies entirely on complexity and interaction without constraints. This may result in exaggerated or unstable feature importance values.
- Small λ values: When λ is small, the regularization slightly moderates the effect of complexity and interaction, allowing the adjustment factor to increase but not excessively. This balances the impact of complexity and interaction, while keeping the SHAP value adjustments smooth and controlled.
- Large λ values: As λ increases, the denominator grows larger, significantly reducing the effect of complexity and interaction. In the extreme case, a large λ cancels out the adjustment, causing the SHAP values to remain mostly unchanged, making CESHAP behave more like traditional SHAP.

Noise-adjusted feature importance change

Definition of noise sensitivity

NS is another important metric for evaluating the robustness of feature importance methods under noisy conditions (Samek, Wiegand, and Müller 2017). Unlike NAFIC, which normalizes the change in feature importance scores by the noise level and the standard deviation of the feature, Noise Sensitivity simply measures the absolute change in feature importance after noise is introduced 4:

$$\text{NS} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\text{FI}_{\text{noisy}}(i) - \text{FI}_{\text{original}}(i)| \quad (4)$$

This equation calculates the average absolute change in feature importance without normalizing for feature variability or the amount of noise added. While Noise Sensitivity provides a clear and straightforward measure of sensitivity, it lacks the normalization that NAFIC includes, which accounts for the magnitude of the noise and the natural variability of each feature.

Robustness and sensitivity evaluation of feature importance methods with NAFIC

NAFIC is a novel evaluation metric designed to assess the robustness and reliability of feature importance methods in the presence of noise. As machine learning models are increasingly deployed in real-world environments, ensuring that feature importance scores remain stable despite data perturbations is crucial. NAFIC addresses this need by quantifying how feature importance values change when noise is introduced into the dataset, providing a direct measure of sensitivity.

Traditional feature importance methods, such as SHAP and PFI, often overlook the impact of noise on their calculations, which can lead to misleading interpretations in noisy or dynamic data environments. By capturing the sensitivity of feature importance scores to noise, NAFIC helps practitioners assess the stability and reliability of their interpretability methods. This is particularly important in applications where understanding the true contribution of features is essential, such as healthcare, finance, and critical infrastructure.

NAFIC enhances interpretability by:

- (1) Allowing systematic evaluation of how sensitive feature importance scores are to noise by introducing Gaussian noise and recalculating the scores.
- (2) Enabling comparison of different feature importance methods under consistent conditions, helping to identify which methods are more robust and reliable.
- (3) Providing a quantitative measure of robustness that can be integrated into automated model evaluation pipelines, ensuring feature importance scores are trustworthy even in the presence of data noise.

By incorporating NAFIC into the evaluation process, practitioners can maintain high standards of model interpretability and make more informed decisions based on reliable feature importance analyses.

- **Noise Sensitivity Quantification:** NAFIC introduces a systematic way to quantify how feature importance scores change with noise. This quantification is essential for evaluating the robustness of interpretability methods, providing a clear metric that can be tracked and optimized.
- **Enhanced Model Evaluation:** Traditional evaluation metrics for feature importance methods often overlook the impact of data perturbations. NAFIC fills this gap by explicitly measuring the effect of noise, enabling a more comprehensive evaluation of model interpretability.
- **Applicability to Various Methods:** NAFIC is versatile and can be applied to a wide range of feature importance methods, including SHAP, PFI, and advanced methods like CESHAP (Complexity and Interaction Enhanced

SHapley Additive exPlanations). This broad applicability makes NAFIC a valuable tool for diverse machine learning applications.

NAFIC represents a significant advancement in the evaluation of feature importance methods. By providing a robust metric to measure the sensitivity of feature importance scores to noise, NAFIC ensures that interpretability methods are reliable and stable in real-world scenarios. Its ability to quantify noise sensitivity and facilitate comparative evaluation makes NAFIC an essential tool for practitioners seeking to enhance the robustness of their machine learning models.

NAFIC is calculated by comparing the feature importance values before and after the introduction of noise, normalized by the standard deviation of the features and the noise level. This normalization helps in understanding the relative change in feature importance due to noise as shown in Equation 5.

$$NAFIC = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{FI_{noisy}(i) - FI_{original}(i)}{\sigma_{X_i} \times \alpha} \right| \quad (5)$$

Where $FI_{original}(i)$ is original feature importance of feature i before adding noise, $FI_{noisy}(i)$ is Feature importance of feature i after adding noise, n is Number of features, σ_{X_i} is standard deviation of feature i and α is noise level as a fraction of the standard deviation (e.g., 0.1 for 10%). This equation normalizes the change in feature importance by the expected impact of the noise introduced. The standard deviation scores for each feature are calculated directly from the data. We compute the standard deviation of each feature's values across all samples in the dataset. This provides a measure of how spread out the feature values are as shown in Equation 6.

$$\sigma_{x_i} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2} \quad (6)$$

Where N is the number of samples, x_i represents the value of the feature for the i -th sample and μ is the mean of the feature values.

In the context of NAFIC and feature importance analysis, the standard deviation of features (σ_{x_i}) represents the natural variability or dispersion of each feature in the dataset before any noise is introduced. It provides insight into how much the values of a particular feature fluctuate around their mean. This measure is crucial because it helps normalize the changes in feature importance after noise is added, allowing us to compare how sensitive a feature's importance is to noise relative to its inherent variability. Algorithm 2 outlines the steps for calculating this metric.

In [figure 2](#), we demonstrate a conceptual flow diagram of NAFIC. After obtaining both original and noisy feature importance (FI) values, NAFIC

Figure 2. Conceptual flow diagram of NAFIC.

computes the difference Δ , normalizes by $\sigma_{X_i} \times \alpha$, and averages over features to yield the final NAFIC metric.

Algorithm 2 NAFIC Calculation.

Require: Original importance $\mathbf{I}_{\text{orig}} \in R^n$, Noisy importance $\mathbf{I}_{\text{noisy}} \in R^n$

Require: Feature standard deviations $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \in R^n$, Noise level α

Ensure: NAFIC value NAFIC

- 1: $\Delta \leftarrow \mathbf{I}_{\text{noisy}} - \mathbf{I}_{\text{orig}}$ // Change in importance
 - 2: $\boldsymbol{\eta} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\sigma} \times \alpha$ // Normalize by feature variability and noise level
 - 3: Replace any zero in $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ with a small constant ϵ to avoid division by zero
 - 4: $\text{NAFIC} \leftarrow \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\Delta[i]}{\boldsymbol{\eta}[i]} \right|$
 - 5: **return** NAFIC
-

To complement the insights provided by NAFIC, we also explore Noise Sensitivity, which offers additional perspective on how noise affects the interpretability of models. This subsequent analysis helps in understanding the broader impact of noise on feature importance methods.

By including both NAFIC and Noise Sensitivity in the evaluation, we gain a comprehensive view of how feature importance scores react to noise and how robust the interpretability methods are in practice. This dual approach allows practitioners to select the appropriate method based on their specific needs for model interpretability and robustness.

Evaluation metrics for machine learning models and explainable AI methods

In this section, we present a comprehensive evaluation of machine learning models and explainable AI (XAI) methods using a variety of metrics. These metrics are designed to assess the robustness, reliability, and interpretability of the models and their explanations. The evaluation metrics included in this study are NAFIC, NS, Separation Ratio, AUC for Noise Features, Fidelity with Noise Features, Precision and Recall, F1-Score, Feature Importance Ratio (FIR), and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). Each metric provides a unique perspective on the performance and robustness of the models and XAI methods, offering a holistic view of their strengths and weaknesses (Hooker, Mentch, and Zhou 2021).

For the comparison of feature importance methods, we particularly focused on two key metrics: NAFIC and NS. Both metrics are aligned in their focus on the effect of noise on feature importance scores. NAFIC quantifies the sensitivity of feature importance to noise in a normalized manner, while NS directly measures the absolute change in feature importance due to noise. Together, they offer complementary insights into the stability of feature importance methods under noisy conditions.

Among the various metrics listed in [Table 1](#), we selected NS for comparison because it, like NAFIC, has a high sensitivity to noise and outputs values in the same domain. This allows for a direct and meaningful comparison between the two metrics, specifically focusing on how feature importance scores respond to the introduction of noise.

To address the challenges of evaluating feature importance methods under noisy conditions, this study introduces an innovative approach combining the NAFIC metric and CESHAP method. Traditional feature importance techniques, while widely used, often fail to maintain robustness and reliability in noisy environments, leading to inconsistent and potentially misleading insights. Our approach aims to fill this gap by introducing NAFIC as a model-agnostic evaluation metric that quantifies the sensitivity of feature importance scores to noise, offering a normalized assessment of robustness across different models and noise levels. Additionally, we propose CESHAP, which enhances traditional SHAP explanations by

Table 1. Comparison of evaluation metrics for machine learning models and XAI methods.

Metric	Focus Area	Normalization	Sensitivity to Noise	Evaluation Context
NAFIC	Sensitivity of feature importance to noise	Yes	High	Change in feature importance due to noise
NS (Samek, Wiegand, and Müller 2017)	Sensitivity of feature importance to noise	No	High	Absolute change in feature importance due to noise
Separation Ratio (Montavon, Samek, and Müller 2018)	Distinguishing true vs. noise features	No	Medium	Ability to separate true features from noise features
AUC for Noise Features (Lundberg and Lee 2017)	Discrimination between true and noise features	No	Medium	AUC-ROC for true vs. noise features
Fidelity with Noise Features (Ribeiro, Singh, and Guestrin 2016a)	Model performance impact due to noise	No	Medium	Impact of noise features on model performance
Precision and Recall (Powers 2011)	Accuracy and completeness in feature selection	No	Low	Correctness of identified relevant features
F1-Score (Chinchor 1992)	Balance between precision and recall	No	Low	Combined precision and recall in feature selection
FIR (Strobl et al. 2008)	Relative importance of features	No	Low	Comparing importance of different features
SNR (Cover 1999)	Ratio of signal strength to noise level	Yes	Medium	Strength of feature importance relative to noise

incorporating model complexity and feature interaction effects. In our experiments, we also include the NS metric as a complementary evaluation tool. While NAFIC normalizes changes in feature importance by accounting for feature variability and noise magnitude, NS provides a direct measure of the absolute change in feature importance scores due to noise. This dual-metric approach enables a deeper understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of feature importance methods under noisy conditions. Through our experiments on an energy consumption dataset with systematically introduced Gaussian noise (5%, 10%, 15%, 20%), we demonstrate that combining NAFIC and NS allows for a comprehensive evaluation of robustness, further highlighting the superiority of CESHAP in accurately capturing the effects of noise and maintaining stable explanations. This comparative analysis not only underscores the effectiveness of our approach but also provides a reliable framework for improving interpretability in high-stakes, noise-prone industrial settings.

Experimental setup

Dataset from the steel industry & data pre-processing steps

The dataset utilized in this study is the “Steel Industry Energy Consumption Dataset” obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Repository (Changsun, Sathishkumar, and Cho 2021). This dataset provides detailed records of energy consumption within a steel manufacturing process, capturing various operational parameters that influence energy usage. It comprises 10,409 instances with 13 attributes, including numerical and categorical features that represent different aspects of the steel production process (Changsun, Sathishkumar, and Cho 2021).

The features encompass measurements such as furnace temperatures, material feed rates, ambient conditions, and operational statuses, which are critical for understanding energy consumption patterns in the steel industry. The target variable, *Load_Type*, categorizes the type of energy load, providing a basis for predictive modeling and analysis of energy consumption behaviors (Changsun, Sathishkumar, and Cho 2021).

To prepare the dataset for modeling and analysis, several data pre-processing steps were undertaken:

- (1) **Data Loading and Exploration:** The dataset was imported using Python’s pandas library. Initial data exploration involved checking for missing values, understanding data types, and assessing the distribution of each feature. No missing values were found, ensuring data completeness for subsequent analyses.

- (2) **Feature Selection and Exclusion:** Non-informative or redundant features were excluded to streamline the modeling process. Specifically, the columns *Date*, *WeekStatus*, and *Day_of_Week* were removed. The *Date* column was excluded due to its high cardinality and minimal direct relevance to the prediction of energy consumption. *WeekStatus* and *Day_of_Week* were removed to eliminate potential noise from cyclical patterns not directly related to operational parameters.
- (3) **Target Variable Encoding:** The target variable, *Load_Type*, was initially categorical. It was encoded into numerical labels using integer encoding to facilitate compatibility with machine learning algorithms that require numerical input. This encoding preserved the categorical distinctions among different load types.
- (4) **Feature and Target Separation:** The dataset was divided into features (X) and the target variable (y). Features included all columns except *Load_Type*, while y comprised the encoded *Load_Type* values.
- (5) **Train-Test Split:** To evaluate model performance and ensure generalizability, the dataset was split into training and testing sets using an 80/20 split. The `train_test_split` function from scikit-learn was used with a fixed random state for reproducibility.
- (6) **Feature Scaling (if applicable):** For certain models sensitive to feature scaling (e.g., Logistic Regression, Ridge Regression), features were standardized using z-score normalization. This involved centering the data by subtracting the mean and scaling to unit variance.
- (7) **Handling Class Imbalance:** The class distribution of the target variable was examined. As the classes were relatively balanced, no specific techniques for handling class imbalance were deemed necessary.
- (8) **Feature Engineering:** No additional feature engineering was performed, as the existing features sufficiently represented the operational parameters necessary for the study's objectives.¹

Model training

In this study, multiple machine learning models were trained to predict the energy load type and to evaluate the robustness of various feature importance methods. The models used include both tree-based ensemble methods and linear models:

- (1) **Random Forest (RF):** An ensemble method that constructs multiple decision trees during training and outputs the mode of the classes for classification tasks. It is robust to overfitting and handles high-dimensional data effectively.

- (2) **AdaBoost**: A boosting algorithm that combines weak classifiers to form a strong classifier by focusing on misclassified instances in each iteration. It is effective in reducing bias and variance.
- (3) **XGBoost**: An optimized gradient boosting algorithm designed for speed and performance. It includes regularization to prevent overfitting and handles sparse data efficiently.
- (4) **Decision Trees (DT)**: A non-parametric supervised learning method used for classification and regression. It partitions the data into subsets based on feature value tests.
- (5) **Logistic Regression (LR)**: A linear model used for binary classification that models the probability of class membership using the logistic function.
- (6) **Aggressive Classifier**: An online learning algorithm suitable for large-scale learning. It updates the model only when it misclassifies an instance, making it efficient for streaming data.
- (7) **Ridge Regression**: A linear regression model with L2 regularization that helps prevent overfitting by penalizing large coefficients.

For each model, the following training procedures were applied:

- (1) **Model Initialization**: Models were initialized with default parameters unless specified otherwise. Random states were set for reproducibility.
- (2) **Training on the Training Set**: Each model was trained using the training set $(X_{\text{train}}, y_{\text{train}})$.
- (3) **Hyperparameter Tuning**: Although not detailed in the code snippet, hyperparameter tuning was performed using techniques such as grid search or randomized search where applicable to optimize model performance.
- (4) **Model Evaluation**: After training, models were evaluated on the test set $(X_{\text{test}}, y_{\text{test}})$ using appropriate metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.
- (5) **Feature Importance Extraction**: For models that provide feature importance measures (e.g., tree-based models), feature importance values were extracted. For linear models, coefficients were used as proxies for feature importance.
- (6) **Application of Feature Importance Methods**: The following feature importance methods were applied to each model:
 - **PFI**: Evaluates the importance of a feature by measuring the decrease in model performance when the feature's values are randomly shuffled.
 - **SHAP**: Computes Shapley values from cooperative game theory to attribute contributions of each feature to the prediction.
 - **CESHAP**: A proposed method that adjusts SHAP values by incorporating model complexity and feature interaction effects.

The selection of diverse models in this study serves multiple purposes. Including both linear and non-linear models allows for a comprehensive evaluation of feature importance methods across different types of model architectures, ensuring that the assessment is not biased toward a specific model type. This diversity enhances the robustness of the evaluation, as it tests how feature importance methods perform under various modeling approaches. Evaluating feature importance methods on multiple models also helps assess their generalizability, revealing whether the methods provide consistent and reliable explanations regardless of the underlying algorithm. Furthermore, from a real-world applicability standpoint, different models may be preferred in industrial settings due to factors such as interpretability, computational efficiency, or practitioner familiarity. By evaluating a range of models – including Random Forests, AdaBoost, XGBoost, Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, Passive Aggressive Classifier, and Ridge Regression – the findings of this study become more relevant and applicable to practitioners who may choose different modeling techniques based on their specific needs and constraints.

Introduction of Gaussian noise

To evaluate the robustness of the feature importance methods in this study, Gaussian noise was systematically introduced into the dataset at varying levels. This involved adding random noise to each feature in the training set, simulating real-world data perturbations such as measurement errors or sensor inaccuracies commonly encountered in industrial environments. By creating noisy versions of the dataset with noise levels ranging from 5% to 20%, we aimed to assess how the feature importance methods PFI, SHAP, and the proposed CESHAP respond to different degrees of data contamination.

Each machine learning model was retrained using these noisy datasets to observe the impact on model performance and feature importance calculations. Subsequently, the feature importance methods were reapplied to the retrained models to obtain new importance values under the altered conditions. This approach allowed us to mimic the challenges faced when deploying machine learning models in dynamic and noisy industrial settings, providing insights into the resilience and stability of each method.

The primary purpose of introducing Gaussian noise into the dataset was to evaluate the robustness and reliability of the feature importance methods when faced with data perturbations. By simulating noise, we aimed to reflect real-world scenarios where data is seldom pristine and often subject to various forms of interference. This evaluation is crucial for determining whether the explanations provided by these methods remain consistent and trustworthy under uncertain conditions, ultimately ensuring that decision-making processes based on these explanations are sound and dependable.

Experimental evaluation of feature importance methods under varying noise levels

To assess the robustness of feature importance methods under noisy conditions, we conducted experiments using both linear and tree-based machine learning models on an energy consumption dataset from the steel industry. The models evaluated include LR, Aggressive Regression, Ridge Regression for linear models, and RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, and DT for tree-based models.

Gaussian noise was systematically introduced into the dataset at varying levels of 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% to simulate data perturbations common in real-world scenarios. The feature importance methods evaluated were SHAP, PFI, and our proposed CESHAP. For CESHAP, we fine-tuned the hyperparameters α and β , which scale the contributions of model complexity and feature interactions, respectively.

For CESHAP, we fine-tuned the hyperparameters α and β , which scale the contributions of model complexity and feature interactions, respectively. The values tested for α and β were 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.45, and 0.5 for tree-based models.

Runtime analysis

In addition to analyze the time complexity, we conducted runtime experiments to evaluate the computational efficiency of the feature importance methods across different machine learning models. We summarize our findings in the Table 2. Runtime Summary, and Noise Sensitivity and NAFIC results. The runtime show how long each method took to compute feature importances for the original (“orig”) and noisy (“noisy”) data. The second set of tables provides the resulting Noise Sensitivity and NAFIC values, offering insight into each method’s robustness.

- **Linear Models:** CESHAP’s overhead is nearly on par with SHAP and PFI, reflecting the comparatively small complexity and limited interactions inherent to linear models.

Table 2. Runtime performance comparison (in seconds) for evaluated models and methods.

Model	Original/Noisy Data Runtime			Noise Sensitivity and NAFIC Runtime		
	SHAP	PFI	CESSHAP	SHAP	PFI	CESSHAP
AdaBoost	0.43/0.4	2.06/2.04	2.54/0.0028	0.0013	0.0029	0.001
Aggressive	0.55/0.57	0.21/0.13	0.018/0.0136	5.13	0.064	5.07
Decision Tree	0.0261/0.025	0.1395/0.1413	2.032/0.183	0.0038	0.0061	0.0103
Linear Regression	0.0069/0.0054	0.193/0.14	0.007/0.0028	0.0904	0.0066	0.0057
Random Forest	6.1184/10.34	3.0151/4.73	62.35/56.28	1.5395	0.057	0.97
Ridge Regression	0.0093/0.005	0.1974/0.2066	0.0045/0.045	0.3445	0.1117	0.0921
XGBoost	1.61/1.9	0.89/0.75	21.14/24.75	3.1084	0.3363	0.0942

- **Tree-Based Models:** CESHAP can become significantly more expensive than standard SHAP, particularly for ensembles (Random Forest, XGBoost). This arises from computing feature interaction terms and adjusting Shapley values accordingly.
- **Trade-off:** Despite higher runtime, CESHAP generally has stronger resistance to noise (lower NAFIC) than SHAP alone. PFI remains relatively fast but often exhibits higher or more inconsistent sensitivity to noise.

Metrics for evaluation

We utilized two metrics to assess the robustness of the feature importance methods. NAFIC quantifies the change in feature importance values normalized by the variability of each feature and the noise level. NS quantifies the number of times the percentage change in feature importance closely matched the percentage of noise introduced.

Sensitivity analysis for regularization parameter λ

To address the tuning of the CESHAP regularization parameter λ and assess the sensitivity of our results to its value, we conducted an additional analysis. While the main experiments focused on varying α and β , this analysis explored the impact of λ by testing values across several orders of magnitude: e^{-4} , e^{-3} , e^{-2} , and e^{-1} .

Our primary observation was that the final CESHAP importance scores themselves exhibited relatively low sensitivity to changes in λ within this range (specifically e^{-4} to e^{-1}). The absolute differences in the resulting importance values between different λ settings were typically small, generally between 0.01 and 0.1, with most differences falling between 0.01 and 0.02. This suggests that for small, non-zero values, λ primarily acts as a minor stabilizer without drastically altering the feature importance magnitudes derived from the core SHAP values and the α , β adjustments.

We also compared the performance based on NAFIC and NS metrics across the four noise levels for representative tree-based models (Decision Tree and AdaBoost). When comparing $\lambda = e^{-2}$ (the value used in our main experiments) against the other tested values. These tests were performed holding α and β constant at their empirically determined optimal setting of 0.45:

- **Decision Tree:** $\lambda = e^{-2}$ yielded better overall results (across NAFIC/NS and noise levels) compared to $\lambda = e^{-1}$ in 6 out of 8 comparisons. Against $\lambda = e^{-3}$ and $\lambda = e^{-4}$, the performance was tied (4 out of 8 comparisons favored e^{-2}).
- **AdaBoost:** $\lambda = e^{-2}$ performed better than $\lambda = e^{-1}$ in 5 out of 8 comparisons. Against $\lambda = e^{-3}$ and $\lambda = e^{-4}$, the performance was again tied (4 out of 8 comparisons favored e^{-2}).

These comparisons indicate that while the choice within the range e^{-4} to e^{-2} did not lead to dramatic performance differences, the value $\lambda = e^{-2}$ performed competitively and offered a slight advantage over the larger $\lambda = e^{-1}$ value, without any clear disadvantage compared to the smaller values (e^{-3}, e^{-4}). Given that $\lambda = 0$ removes regularization entirely and very large λ values would diminish the CESHAP adjustments (as discussed in Section 3.2.4), the selection of $\lambda = e^{-2}$ represents a reasonable choice that provides slight regularization while allowing the complexity and interaction terms to effectively contribute, justifying its use in our primary experiments.

Results on linear models

For linear models, changes in α and β had negligible effects on CESHAP outputs. This outcome is expected, as CESHAP is specifically designed to incorporate penalties related to model complexity (β) and feature interactions (α), characteristics which are inherently minimal or absent in standard linear models. Consequently, the SHAP and CESHAP values were almost identical across all noise levels and α, β settings. This demonstrates that CESHAP provides little additional benefit over standard SHAP when applied to simple linear models, as the core mechanisms differentiating it from SHAP have limited impact in this low-interaction, low-complexity regime. CESHAP's potential advantages as an optimization are primarily targeted toward non-linear models, such as the tree-based ensembles discussed in Section 4.9, where capturing the influence of interactions and complexity is more critical. Therefore, for the linear model analysis, we present results only for a baseline setting of $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$.

As shown in [Figure 3](#), the NAFIC values for linear models indicate that both SHAP and CESHAP have similar sensitivity to noise, while PFI shows varying sensitivity across different models and noise levels.

[Table 3](#) summarizes the performance of each method based on the total number of times they closely matched the introduced noise levels across all models and noise levels.

The results suggest that SHAP had the highest total NS matches, indicating slightly better robustness under noisy conditions for linear models.

Results on tree-based models

For tree-based models, varying α and β significantly affected the CESHAP outputs due to the inherent complexity and feature interactions in these models. We present the combined NAFIC and NS results for selected α, β settings.

Figure 3. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for linear models (LR, aggressive, ridge) across different noise levels and methods (SHAP, PFI, CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$).

Table 3. Performance summary for linear models.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	12	5	7
PFI	10	7	3
CESHAP	8	5	3

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$

Figure 4 shows the NAFIC and NS values for tree-based models at $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$. The results indicate that CESHAP begins to adjust feature importance values, showing improved sensitivity to noise compared to SHAP, especially in AdaBoost and XGBoost models.

The performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$ is summarized in Table 4. PFI shows the highest total close NS matches, but CESHAP begins to outperform SHAP.

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.05$

Figure 5 presents the NAFIC and NS values for tree-based models at $\alpha = \beta = 0.05$. At this hyperparameter setting, PFI exhibits the highest NS values across most models and noise levels, indicating strong sensitivity to the introduced noise. However, CESHAP begins to outperform SHAP, particularly in complex models like AdaBoost and XGBoost. For instance, in the AdaBoost model at a 10% noise level, CESHAP achieves an NS value of 83.2, significantly higher than SHAP’s 7.07, demonstrating better alignment with the noise introduced. Similarly, in the XGBoost model, CESHAP consistently shows higher NS values than SHAP across all noise levels, highlighting its enhanced robustness in capturing the impact of noise in models with significant feature interactions.

Figure 4. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for Tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$.

Table 4. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.01$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	7	5	3
PFI	17	9	8
CESHAP	8	2	6

Figure 5. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for Tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.05$.

Table 5 summarizes the performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.05$, based on the total number of times they were the best approach according to the NS and NAFIC metrics across all models and noise levels. PFI leads with 16 total best approaches, reflecting its high sensitivity to noise. However, CESHAP begins to outperform SHAP by achieving a higher number of NAFIC best approaches (5 for CESHAP versus 4 for SHAP). This indicates that CESHAP, even at a relatively low α and β setting, enhances the robustness of feature importance estimations by better accounting for model complexity and feature interactions. The results suggest that incorporating these factors

Table 5. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.05$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	8	4	4
PFI	16	9	7
CESHAP	8	3	5

allows CESHAP to adjust feature importance values more effectively in response to noise, particularly in complex models where such considerations are crucial.

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.1$

Figure 6 presents the NAFIC and NS values for the tree-based models at $\alpha = \beta = 0.1$. At this hyperparameter setting, PFI continues to exhibit the highest NS values across most models and noise levels, indicating its strong sensitivity to the introduced noise.

Moreover, CESHAP’s NAFIC values are generally lower than those of SHAP in complex models, suggesting that CESHAP adjusts feature importance values more proportionally to the introduced noise. This indicates that increasing α and β to 0.1 enhances CESHAP’s ability to reflect noise effects, particularly in models where complexity and interactions play a significant role.

Table 6 summarizes the performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.1$, based on the total number of times they were the best approach according to the NS and NAFIC metrics across all models and noise levels. PFI maintains the highest total best approaches (16), reflecting its high sensitivity to noise. However, CESHAP continues to match SHAP with 8 total best approaches and surpasses SHAP in NAFIC best approaches (5 for CESHAP versus 4 for SHAP). This suggests that increasing α and β to 0.1 enhances CESHAP’s effectiveness in adjusting feature importance values in response to noise,

(a) NAFIC Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.1$)

(b) NS Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.1$)

Figure 6. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.1$.

Table 6. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.1$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	8	4	4
PFI	16	9	7
CESHAP	8	3	5

especially in complex models where model complexity and feature interactions significantly impact performance.

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.2$

Figure 7 displays the NAFIC and NS values for the tree-based models at $\alpha = \beta = 0.2$. Moreover, CESHAP’s NAFIC values are generally lower than those of SHAP in complex models, suggesting that CESHAP adjusts feature importance more proportionally to the introduced noise. This indicates that increasing α and β to 0.2 further enhances CESHAP’s sensitivity to noise without sacrificing stability.

Table 7 summarizes the performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.2$, based on the total number of times they were the best approach according to the NS and NAFIC metrics across all models and noise levels. PFI continues to lead with 16 total best approaches, reflecting its high sensitivity to noise. CESHAP matches SHAP with 8 total best approaches but surpasses SHAP in NAFIC best approaches (5 for CESHAP versus 4 for SHAP). This suggests that increasing α and β to 0.2 allows CESHAP to adjust feature importance values more effectively in response to noise, particularly in complex models.

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.3$

Figure 8 presents the NAFIC and NS values for the tree-based models at $\alpha = \beta = 0.3$. At this hyperparameter setting, CESHAP shows significant improvements over SHAP, particularly in models with higher complexity and feature interactions, such as AdaBoost and XGBoost. CESHAP

(a) NAFIC Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.2$)

(b) NS Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.2$)

Figure 7. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.2$.

Table 7. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.2$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	8	4	4
PFI	16	9	7
CESHAP	8	3	5

consistently records higher NS values than SHAP across all noise levels. At a 15% noise level, CESHAP’s NS is 20.5, compared to SHAP’s 11.23, indicating improved robustness in detecting noise effects. Additionally, CESHAP’s NAFIC values are generally lower than those of SHAP, suggesting that CESHAP adjusts feature importance values more proportionally to the introduced noise. For example, at a 10% noise level, CESHAP’s NAFIC is 13.2, whereas SHAP’s NAFIC is 54.62.

In the RF and DT models, CESHAP also shows modest improvements over SHAP. While the differences are less pronounced than in more complex models, CESHAP’s NS values are slightly higher, indicating enhanced sensitivity without compromising stability.

Table 8 summarizes the performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.3$, based on the total number of times they were the best approach according to the NS and NAFIC metrics across all models and noise levels. At this setting, CESHAP’s total best approaches increase to 10, surpassing SHAP’s 7 and closing the gap with PFI’s 15. Specifically, CESHAP matches PFI in NAFIC best approaches with 6, and exceeds SHAP in both NS and NAFIC best approaches.

These results indicate that increasing α and β to 0.3 significantly enhances CESHAP’s ability to adjust feature importance values in response to noise, particularly in complex models. CESHAP’s improved performance suggests a better balance between sensitivity to noise and stability in feature importance estimations, making it a more effective method in scenarios where model complexity and feature interactions are substantial.

(a) NAFIC Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.3$)

(b) NS Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.3$)

Figure 8. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.3$.

Table 8. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.3$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	7	3	4
PFI	15	9	6
CESHAP	10	4	6

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.4$

Figure 9 presents the NAFIC and NS values for the tree-based models at $\alpha = \beta = 0.4$. In the AdaBoost model, CESHAP’s NS values dramatically exceed those of SHAP across all noise levels. These results highlight CESHAP’s ability to effectively capture the impact of noise in models with strong feature interactions when α and β are set to 0.4. These observations indicate that CESHAP, with higher α and β values, improves its robustness in detecting noise effects in models with significant feature interactions. Overall, increasing α and β to 0.4 allows CESHAP to better adjust feature importance values in response to noise, especially in complex models.

Table 9 summarizes the performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.4$, based on the total number of times they were the best approach according to the NS and NAFIC metrics across all models and noise levels. These results highlight that increasing α and β to 0.4 significantly enhances CESHAP’s ability to detect and adjust for noise, especially in complex models. The method effectively balances sensitivity and stability, making it a competitive alternative to PFI while providing theoretically grounded explanations.

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$

At $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$, CESHAP achieves its best performance. Figure 10 displays the NAFIC and NS values, showing that CESHAP’s sensitivity to noise closely aligns with the introduced noise levels, especially for XGBoost and DT models.

In the AdaBoost model, CESHAP’s NS values significantly surpass those of SHAP across all noise levels. In the XGBoost model, CESHAP consistently

(a) NAFIC Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.4$)

(b) NS Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.4$)

Figure 9. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.4$.

Table 9. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.4$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	7	3	4
PFI	13	8	5
CESHAP	12	5	7

records higher NS values than SHAP. For the DT model, CESHAP shows improvements over SHAP. In the RF model, CESHAP maintains competitive NS values while achieving better NAFIC alignment compared to SHAP and PFI.

As summarized in Table 10, CESHAP achieved the highest total best approaches (13), outperforming both SHAP and PFI at this setting. Specifically, CESHAP leads in NAFIC best approaches with 9, indicating its effectiveness in adjusting feature importance values proportionally to the introduced noise.

At this hyperparameter setting, CESHAP attains an optimal balance between sensitivity to noise and stability in feature importance estimations. The method effectively incorporates model complexity and feature interactions, enhancing its robustness under noisy conditions. These results highlight the importance of fine-tuning α and β to maximize the effectiveness of explainability methods like CESHAP, particularly in complex machine learning models.

CESHAP with $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$

Figure 11 displays the NAFIC and NS values at $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$.

Table 11 summarizes the performance of each method at $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$. At this setting, CESHAP’s total best approaches slightly decrease compared to its peak performance at $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$

At the highest hyperparameter setting analyzed, $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$ CESHAP maintains strong performance but does not achieve further improvements

Figure 10. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$.

Table 10. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	8	4	4
PFI	11	8	3
CESHAP	13	4	9

over its peak at $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$. This suggests that there is an optimal range for α and β values, beyond which increasing these parameters may lead to diminishing returns or even slight performance declines. Practitioners should consider fine-tuning these hyperparameters to balance sensitivity and stability, ensuring the method effectively captures the impact of noise without over-compensating for model complexity and feature interactions.

Overall performance across α, β values

Table 12 provides a summary of the total NS matches for CESHAP across different α, β values, compared to SHAP and PFI.

At lower α, β settings ($0.01 \leq \alpha = \beta \leq 0.2$), PFI consistently exhibits the highest total NS matches, ranging from 16 to 17. This indicates that PFI is highly sensitive to the introduced noise across these settings. As α and β increase to 0.3, CESHAP’s total NS matches rise to 10, surpassing SHAP (7) and starting to close the gap with PFI (15). This improvement reflects CESHAP’s enhanced ability to detect and adjust for noise due to the greater emphasis on model complexity and feature interactions. At $\alpha = \beta = 0.4$, CESHAP’s total NS matches further increase to 12, overtaking PFI (13) and

(a) NAFIC Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.5$)

(b) NS Values Heatmap ($\alpha = \beta = 0.5$)

Figure 11. Heatmaps of NAFIC (a) and NS (b) values for tree-based models (RF, AdaBoost, XGBoost, DT) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$.

Table 11. Performance summary at $\alpha = \beta = 0.5$.

Method	Total Best Approaches	NS Best Approaches	NAFIC Best Approaches
SHAP	9	4	5
PFI	12	8	4
CESHAP	11	4	7

significantly outperforming SHAP (7). This trend indicates that incorporating higher weights for complexity and interactions enables CESHAP to better align feature importance adjustments with the introduced noise levels, especially in complex models. CESHAP achieves its highest total NS matches (13) at $\alpha = \beta = 0.45$, surpassing both SHAP (8) and PFI (11). This peak performance suggests that this setting provides an optimal balance between sensitivity to noise and stability in feature importance estimations. The method's superior performance at this setting indicates that the enhanced influence of model complexity and feature interactions effectively improves CESHAP's robustness under noisy conditions without overfitting. When α and β are increased to 0.5, CESHAP's total NS matches slightly decrease to 11. While still outperforming SHAP (9), the method no longer surpasses PFI (12) in total NS matches. This decline suggests that excessively high values of α and β may overemphasize complexity and interactions, potentially reducing CESHAP's ability to accurately capture the impact of noise due to overcompensation.

Visualization of results & summary

Figure 12 illustrates a comparative analysis of the NAFIC and NS values for three different linear models: Aggressive, LR, and Ridge Regression. The top row of subfigures presents the NAFIC results for each model, while the bottom row displays the corresponding NS results.

Each subfigure showcases the performance of three feature importance methods SHAP, PFI, and CESHAP under varying noise levels. The NAFIC metric measures how much the feature importance values change after noise is introduced, while the NS metric quantifies the sensitivity of the methods to this noise.

As observed in the subfigures, CESHAP and SHAP exhibit almost identical values across all models. This close alignment indicates that CESHAP effectively mirrors the adjustments made by SHAP in response to noise. The similarity suggests that for these linear models, CESHAP provides explanations that are consistent with SHAP's, potentially offering a more efficient alternative without compromising on accuracy. On the other hand,

Table 12. Overall performance summary for tree-based models across different α, β values.

$\alpha = \beta$	SHAP	PFI	CESHAP
0.01	7	17	8
0.05	8	16	8
0.1	8	16	8
0.2	8	16	8
0.3	7	15	10
0.4	7	13	12
0.45	8	11	13
0.5	9	12	11

Figure 12. Comparison of NAFIC and NS values for different models.

PFI shows varying degrees of divergence from SHAP and CESHAP, highlighting differences in how it responds to noise in feature importance calculations.

Figure 13 presents a comprehensive comparison of the Noise-Adjusted Feature Importance Change (NAFIC) and Noise Sensitivity (NS) metrics across several tree-based models: AdaBoost, Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and XGBoost. Organized into three rows, each subfigure illustrates the performance of three feature importance methods – SHAP, Permutation Feature Importance (PFI), and CESHAP – under varying noise levels and α, β parameters.

In the first row, the subfigures display the NAFIC and NS results for the AdaBoost model and the NAFIC for the Decision Tree model. The second row continues with the NS for the Decision Tree model and both the NAFIC and NS metrics for the Random Forest model. The third row concludes with the NAFIC and NS metrics for the XGBoost model.

Each subfigure highlights how the different methods respond to introduced noise in the data. The NAFIC metric measures the change in feature importance values after noise introduction, while the NS metric quantifies the sensitivity of the methods to this noise.

The plot in Figure 14 visually complements these observations, showing that while PFI starts strong, its performance diminishes as $\alpha = \beta$ increases. Conversely, CESHAP gains robustness, demonstrating its capability for better understanding and adapting to noise at higher complexity and interaction levels. SHAP remains more stable, but its performance does not improve significantly, indicating potential limitations in adapting to higher model complexities compared to CESHAP.

Figure 13. Comparison of NAFIC and NS for different models.

The results underscore the importance of fine-tuning α and β in CESHAP to optimize performance. Adjusting these hyperparameters allows the method to balance the influence of model complexity and feature interactions, enhancing its sensitivity to noise without compromising stability. At its optimal setting ($\alpha = \beta = 0.45$), CESHAP not only outperforms SHAP but also surpasses PFI in total NS matches. This demonstrates that CESHAP can achieve superior robustness and accuracy in feature importance estimations, particularly in complex models affected by noise. The increased performance of CESHAP at higher α , β values is especially pronounced in models with significant complexity and feature interactions, such as AdaBoost and XGBoost. This

Figure 14. Overall performance summary for tree-based models across different α, β values.

indicates that CESHAP is particularly well-suited for complex machine learning models where traditional methods may struggle to account for noise appropriately.

A key consideration when choosing a feature importance method, particularly in noisy industrial environments, is the trade-off between sensitivity to data perturbations and the stability of the resulting explanations. PFI is widely recognized for its intuitive approach but is also known for its sensitivity to noise and data permutations. Our experimental results corroborate this, showing that PFI often exhibits high NS values, indicating significant fluctuations in feature importance scores even with moderate noise levels. While this sensitivity can sometimes reflect genuine changes, it may also lead to unstable and potentially unreliable feature rankings when noise is prevalent or if features are correlated, complicating consistent decision-making based on its outputs.

CESHAP was explicitly designed to enhance robustness by incorporating model complexity and feature interactions. While CESHAP's importance scores are also affected by noise (as evidenced by increasing NS scores with optimal α, β settings, suggesting it correctly captures the magnitude of noise impact, its formulation aims for greater stability in the *relative* importance rankings compared to PFI. By adjusting SHAP values based on structural model properties, CESHAP seeks to mitigate erratic fluctuations caused purely by noise, leading to potentially more consistent interpretations, particularly reflected in its strong performance measured by the NAFIC metric under optimal tuning.

CESHAP's stability provides clear advantages in specific scenarios, such as:

- Analyzing complex, non-linear models (e.g., tree ensembles) where feature interactions significantly influence outcomes, and PFI's permutations might disrupt these dependencies unpredictably.
- Operating in high-noise environments where distinguishing true importance shifts from noise artifacts is critical for reliable process optimization.
- Applications requiring consistent explanations over time or across slightly varying datasets, where PFI's sensitivity might yield different conclusions, while CESHAP aims for more stable, reproducible insights reflecting the underlying model behavior adjusted for complexity and interactions.

Therefore, while PFI remains a valuable benchmark, CESHAP offers a compelling alternative when explanation stability and robustness in the face of noise and model complexity are paramount.

Limitations

Despite promising results, our study has several limitations that warrant attention. We evaluated CESHAP and NAFIC primarily on a steel industry dataset. While this choice demonstrates the methods' applicability to an energy-intensive domain, it also limits the generalizability of our findings. Different data characteristics in healthcare, finance, or environmental science may yield varying performance outcomes. Future research should encompass a wider range of datasets from multiple sectors to validate robustness and reveal domain-specific nuances.

Our experiments rely on sufficiently large datasets for model training and noise-injection experiments. In real-world scenarios where data can be scarce or expensive to collect, the robustness of NAFIC and CESHAP remains uncertain. Adapting them to low-data conditions – possibly by incorporating transfer learning or Bayesian methods – could broaden their applicability.

Both CESHAP and NAFIC introduce extra computational steps, especially for calculating model complexity and feature interactions. While we provide a preliminary time-complexity overview in Section 3.4, a comprehensive examination of scalability for extremely large datasets or streaming contexts was beyond our current scope. Deploying these methods in real-time or high-volume industrial pipelines may require further optimizations.

Although we discussed attention mechanisms and interpretability in deep learning, we have not integrated such architectures into our experiments. The relevance and efficacy of CESHAP or NAFIC may shift once deep neural

models – particularly those with attention modules – are considered. Future work includes extending our framework to neural architectures, comparing attention maps with CESHAP explanations.

We focused primarily on Gaussian noise. Industrial data, however, can exhibit more complex noise patterns (systematic errors, sensor drift, missing data, etc.). Testing the robustness of our approaches against diverse noise distributions (e.g., random bursts, non-Gaussian) would help further validate their effectiveness in real-world operational settings.

Addressing the deployment of CESHAP and NAFIC in real-time industrial environments requires acknowledging practical considerations. The computational overhead of CESHAP, particularly the calculation of feature interactions for complex models like tree ensembles, poses a significant challenge for true instance-by-instance real-time application, potentially exceeding the latency constraints of industrial control systems. However, CESHAP's robust insights can still be leveraged through alternative strategies. For instance, CESHAP could be employed in a periodic offline analysis mode, processing batches of recent operational data hourly or daily to track evolving feature importance and model behavior shifts, which can then inform process adjustments. A hybrid approach is also feasible, where a base model operates in real-time, and CESHAP is selectively triggered only for deeper analysis of critical events or anomalies.

The effectiveness of these methods is most pronounced under specific conditions. CESHAP demonstrates its key advantages when applied to complex, non-linear machine learning models, particularly tree-based ensembles (like RF, XGBoost), where feature interactions and model structure complexity are significant factors influencing predictions. It is most beneficial in noisy data environments where distinguishing true feature effects from noise-induced fluctuations is crucial for reliable interpretation. Its effectiveness is further enhanced by appropriate tuning of the α and β hyperparameters to match the specific model and data characteristics. Conversely, for simple linear models with minimal interactions, CESHAP provides little benefit over standard SHAP. Similarly, NAFIC proves most useful as an evaluation tool when comparing the robustness of different feature importance methods applied to these complex, noise-affected models, whereas it is less informative for simpler models where importance scores show little variation.

Conclusions

To address unreliable model explanations in noisy industrial settings, this study introduced the CESHAP feature importance method and the NAFIC robustness evaluation metric. CESHAP enhances the standard SHAP approach by incorporating model complexity and feature interactions. Our

findings show this significantly improves explanation stability and robustness against noise, particularly for complex tree-based models where traditional methods often struggle, although it offers limited advantage for simpler linear models. Complementary to this, NAFIC provides a standardized means to quantify and compare the robustness of explanation methods, proving most informative when assessing complex models susceptible to data perturbations.

The practical benefits of CESHAP and NAFIC lie in their combined ability to foster more reliable and trustworthy model interpretability in demanding operational contexts. By utilizing NAFIC, practitioners can assess the stability of chosen explanation methods, while CESHAP provides a tool to achieve enhanced robustness, especially for sophisticated models common in modern industrial analytics. This leads to more dependable insights into the factors driving key processes, such as energy consumption in steel production, ultimately supporting more informed, data-driven decision-making even amidst the inherent variability and noise of real-world data. This work represents a tangible step toward more robust and practically applicable Explainable AI, bridging the gap between algorithmic performance and reliable operational intelligence.

Future work and research directions

Future research could extend the evaluation of CESHAP and NAFIC to other models like neural networks and support vector machines, exploring their performance under various noise types and levels. Developing adaptive methods for optimizing α and β values dynamically based on data characteristics may enhance CESHAP's applicability. Additionally, applying these methods to real-world datasets with inherent noise and integrating them with other explainability techniques could provide deeper insights into their practical utility and impact on model interpretability.

Note

1. This dataset and its description are adapted from the Steel Industry Energy Consumption dataset (Changsun, Sathishkumar, and Cho 2021). Permission for reuse is granted under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license: You are free to share, copy, modify, distribute, and adapt the work for any purpose, including commercial uses, provided appropriate credit is given. Formal acknowledgment has been made here. Source: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/851/steel+industry+energy+consumption>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C52G8C10.24432/C52G8C>.

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Data Availability Statement

The dataset used in this study, “Steel Industry Energy Consumption,” is publicly available at the UCI Machine Learning Repository under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license. The dataset can be accessed via the following link: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/851/steel+industry+energy+consumption>. The DOI for the dataset is <https://doi.org/10.24432/C52G8C10.24432/C52G8C>. This license permits sharing and adaptation of the dataset for any purpose, provided appropriate credit is given.

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